

RESPONSE PAPER

LAST NAME: Gajathar

FIRST NAME: Ashvena

PROGRAM CODE: DIPH

COURSE CODE : ACA-401D

PERIOD NUMBER: 01

INSTRUCTOR: Dr Gulma

Edit or delete text to show the actual information below:

The author applied US XUK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics (only keep US or UK)

The student must use Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:

The author did Xdid *not* use Zotero to insert references (remove unneeded text to indicate)

The author did did *not* use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID) (remove unneeded text)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is: 2%

The author used the following software (e.g., MSWord 2016 on Windows 8)

List 5 to 7 critical concepts with page number in text (then bold these terms in your RP)(samples below):

1. The Why Behind Writing a Good Essay (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021, 7)
2. The Humble Punctuation (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021, 8)
3. My Words or Not – Plagiarism (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021, 34-39)
4. A Set of Standards behind Essays – Style Guide (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021, 44-56)
5. Bonnet or Hood – American vs. British English (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021, 25 – 30)

THE ESSENTIAL OF AN ACADEMIC ESSAY

1) INTRODUCTION

“The steps for rigidly linear essays are not necessary” (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021, 7). My first thoughts were that it most certainly is. Many of us may recall our academic years and wonder, when a professor reads our essays, how can they tell almost immediately whether we have done an excellent job or not? This seems to lie in the fact that “Nearly all academic writing shares some kind of formal prose register, citations, and references to other works” (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021, 7-11).

Essays are written in many different styles and are something we have encountered in early school to college and post-graduate years. I have always been favorable to the narrative style of writing in which the story’s point is expressed from learning experiences and why it made an impression on me. However, essay writing is more complex than the story. In this paper, I will discuss academic essay writing, focusing on five concepts: writing a good essay, punctuation, plagiarism, the style guide, and American vs British English.

2) **THE WHY BEHIND THE ESSAY**

It would be essential to determine where one should start to write a good essay. The coursework, as described by the authors, cites, “Defining the question and analyzing the task: While defining and writing everything one knows about a topic is important, analyzing and presenting the answers to strongly agree that a research topic is one of the most critical steps of the writing process. the question is key” (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021, 7).

The authors further highlight the importance of answering questions about how much you know about the topic, whether the material generated is helpful to the arguments presented on the subject, and whether your response can be supported. Therefore, ensuring that the selected topic clarifies the research goal would be prudent.

i) *Writing the Essay*

In my profession within a pharmaceutical organization, research publications are frequently used to support the merit of the efficacy and safety of a drug. A common practice in the industry was reading the abstract of a publication and using this to determine that this is a “good, excellent” publication to support commercial claims of a drug.

Admittedly, I have done the same and found it challenging to understand the critical evaluation that academia would express when reading the complete publication and not accepting the claims that the industry was determined to take on the abstract of a research publication. Of course, this opinion has left me open to thinking differently after reading some of the course content.

ii) *Organizing your Thoughts*

Even though Shakespeare said, “The pen is mightier than the sword,” “the pen itself is not enough to make a good writer. As a new candidate in the program, I have already explored a grand idea for a research topic without due consideration of questioning the structure required for essay writing.

However, the guidelines for the coursework clearly describe that a structured, organized framework as a base requirement to follow a format for the introduction, body, and conclusion is necessary to develop a well-researched outcome.

3) **THE HUMBLE PUNCTUATION**

One of the most used punctuations is the comma, and it is used spontaneously without much thought as to the meaning of the comma. The assigned study material (video), delivered by Prof Laurent Cleenewerck, recommends that sentences be simple and that commas be appropriately used. EUCLID coursework suggests using as little

punctuation as possible. (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021, 16). I have learned numerous rules for using commas, one of which is for adding descriptive information. The comma is not to be used where defining information is used at the start of a sentence.

Another simple but pertinent learning is not to punctuate at the end of a list of bullet points, and punctuation should be used when a bullet point forms a complete sentence with preceding text (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021, 18).

Working through the chapter on punctuation has made me realize that writing a good essay is not just about the words written but about their order. Using punctuation allows for a clear understanding of the message being conveyed.

4) MY WORDS OR NOT - PLAGIARISM

Academic essays MUST contain references that prevent the offense of plagiarism. Cleenewerck and Gulma describe plagiarism as when the writer uses a source of information without giving credit to the author of that source of information (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021, 34). Ensuring that the correct author and source citations are used to avoid plagiarism would be critical. The two methods of citation are “in-text citation and list work citation.

i) *In-Text Citation*

For example, in-text citation “Refers to citing the work you are using within the text itself. When you cite something in the text of your paper, you need to put the author’s name in parenthesis with the page number that the information came from” (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021,35).

ii) *List Citation*

List citations should follow different formats for different works. As an example of online work:

Online books are referenced like a book: author name, date, book title, place of publication, and publisher.

For a website: Author. Title of the site, name of any editors listed, date the URL was accessed, and the URL in brackets (<URL>) (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021, 38).

5) A SET OF STANDARDS BEHIND ESSAYS – STYLE GUIDE

Many different styles of writing exist across diverse disciplines. “A style guide is a means of documenting your approach as a writer to certain elements of writing style that

must be consistent. Style guides are generally associated with certain types of writing like technical writing, commercial or business writing, journalism, and web copywriting” (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021, 41).

The innate standard of English writing style is sufficient for any writer. Still, I have conceptualized that beyond grammar and vocabulary, many other elements define the writing style (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021, 41-43). How a writer writes can be characteristic of that author. This can be seen in the expression of thought, the language used, and the choices of words. As an example of a style of writing by well-known author Ernest Hemingway, “Every day is a new day. It is better to be lucky. But I would rather be exact. Then, when luck comes, you are ready” (Hemingway 1995). Hemingway is well known for his distinctive style of prose writing.

Although EUCLID recommends the Chicago Rules (Turabian), I have noted that I will need to understand my writing style to enable a robust academic response as recommended by EUCLID.

6) BONNET OR HOOD – AMERICAN VS BRITISH ENGLISH

As a South African-born Indian, the interaction between people of English-speaking heritage was prevented. Hence, several varieties of the English language, mainly phonetically, have been adopted by the Indian population. Several South African English varieties have emerged due to Dutch, Portuguese, and British English influences, making South African English unique in its own way.

Some words in South African English were used in British English a long time ago but are no longer used, such as geyser vs boiler or water pump and robot vs traffic light (Esteves 2010). Hence, by this rich history of languages in South Africa, I am naturally more inclined to British English.

However, the learnings of the coursework have shown that American English has grown steadily in international significance since World War II and is currently the dominant influence on “world English” (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021, 25).

I have always perceived British English as more formal than American English, attributed primarily to pronunciation. However, the EUCLID coursework states that American and British English are more similar than different, especially with educated or scientific English. My prejudice to British English had me profoundly thinking about this; my choice for this response paper was British English. The video material presented by Prof Cleenewerck also suggests American English for academic writing. This is a lesson that I have learned, and it has created more awareness for me to pursue my writing style with American English.

7) CONCLUSION

How often have we heard that learnings occur every day? From all I have gained in this first lesson, I am most certainly enthused to continue further into this doctorate program. My initial thoughts were to read the guidelines and process information I have been exposed to in previous courses.

But this first reading has been a pleasant journey and made me realize the importance of a well-structured framework to determine well-conducted research. In my daily work life, I am constantly analyzing scientific publications, barely considering the importance of choosing the research topic, the style of writing, and the language used. I have learned that all of these elements are essential for academic writing, which leaves me determined to master the EUCLID writing style.

REFERENCES

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Gulma. 2021. *ACA-401/ACA-401D Course pack: Period 1*. Fourth edition. Bangui: Euclid University.

Esteves, Vanessa Reis. 2010. "Varieties of English: South African English". Accessed February 23, 2024. https://www.yumpu.com/en/document/view/3915475/varieties-of-english-south-african-english-by-vanessa-reis-esteves-#google_vignette.

Hemingway, Ernest. 1995. *The Old Man and the Sea*. Germany: Max Hueber Verlag.

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. *ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1*. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.